

Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya: Life and Works

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Abstract

Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya (1909–1990) occupies a significant place in the history of Bengali children’s literature and science fiction. Emerging from a literary family environment, he combined scientific knowledge with literary imagination to produce a distinctive body of work that popularized science among young readers. This study examines Bhattacharya’s life, literary career, and intellectual contributions with particular emphasis on his science-fiction narratives and his role in shaping children’s literature in Bengal. The research highlights the interrelationship between his scientific background and creative writings, which enabled him to construct narratives that integrated scientific awareness, curiosity, and moral imagination. Besides his literary works, Bhattacharya’s editorial leadership of the children’s magazine *Ramdhanu* and his role in establishing the *Shishu Sahitya Parishad* significantly contributed to nurturing a culture of children’s literature in Bengal. Through an exploration of his writings, editorial practices, and institutional contributions, the study evaluates his distinctive position within the broader tradition of Bengali science-based literature and children’s literature.

Keywords

Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya; Bengali Science Fiction; Children’s Literature; *Ramdhanu* Magazine; Popular Science Writing; Bengali Literary Culture; Science and Literature.

Introduction

The relationship between a literary work and the life of its creator often provides important insights into the nature and significance of the text. Understanding the social, intellectual, and cultural context of a writer helps in interpreting the thematic concerns and artistic vision reflected in their works. In the context of Bengali literature, Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya represents an important figure whose literary output bridges the domains of science and imagination.

Born in 1909 in Faridpur (present-day Bangladesh), Bhattacharya grew up in a culturally vibrant and intellectually stimulating family environment. His father Bishweshwar Bhattacharya and his elder brother Monoranjan Bhattacharya were both associated with literary activities, which significantly shaped his early intellectual formation. This environment fostered his interest in literature from a young age while his formal education in chemistry at Presidency College and the University of Calcutta gave him a strong scientific foundation.

Bhattacharya’s literary career developed alongside his academic background in science. While teaching chemistry in several colleges in Kolkata, he simultaneously cultivated an extensive career as a writer and editor. His works, particularly those related to science and science fiction, were published in various prominent children’s magazines such as *Ramdhanu*, *Sandesh*, *Shuktara*, and *Kishor Bharati*. Through these writings he sought to stimulate scientific curiosity among young readers while presenting imaginative narratives grounded in scientific possibilities.

In addition to his literary works, Bhattacharya’s contribution as the editor of the children’s magazine *Ramdhanu* and as the founder of the *Shishu Sahitya Parishad* played a crucial role in shaping the landscape of Bengali children’s literature. His efforts helped create a platform for both established and emerging writers and encouraged the development of a vibrant culture of children’s literature. Therefore, an examination of his life and works provides valuable insights into the evolution of Bengali science-based literature and children’s literary traditions.

Objective of study

The primary aim of this study is to examine the life, literary career, and intellectual contributions of Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya, with special emphasis on his science-fiction writings and his role in the development of Bengali children’s literature. The study also seeks to analyze the interaction between science and imagination in his works and to evaluate his contributions as an editor, organizer, and promoter of children’s literary culture.

Research Questions

1. How did Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya’s scientific background influence his literary works, particularly his science-fiction narratives?
2. What role did his editorial activities, especially in the magazine Ramdhanu, play in shaping Bengali children’s literature?
3. In what ways did Bhattacharya contribute to the popularization of science among young readers through literature?
4. How does his work establish a distinctive position within the tradition of Bengali science fiction and children’s literature?

Review of Literature

Earlier, we have received some brief discussions about the life and works of Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya in Samsad Bangali Charitabhidhan, in Sahitya Sangi by Shishir Kumar Das, in a memoir written by Leela Majumdar in the first Children’s Festival issue of Sabuj Pata published by the Shishu-Kishore Akademi, in an article by Ansar Ul Haque in the journal Dipon titled “Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya Ajo Prasongik” (Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya is Still Relevant), in an article by Parthajit Gangopadhyay in Ekdin titled “Jar Hate Bigyan o Sahityer Melbandhan” (The One Who United Science and Literature), in an article by Santu Bag published in Kalpabishwo titled “Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya: Bangla Kalpobigyane Ek Bismrita Adhyay” (Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya: A Forgotten Chapter of Bengali Science Fiction), and to some extent in a chapter of the book Bangla Sahitye Kalpabigyane written by Sourav Bandyopadhyay.

However, through these scattered and in some cases repetitive essays, it has not been possible to gain a comprehensive understanding of Kshitindranarayan’s overall personality and his greater contribution to the world of literature and culture. Therefore, the aim of the present chapter and the following chapters is to present this literary figure to contemporary readers in a holistic manner. He is a literary practitioner who opened before Bengali readers a valuable treasure of science fiction along with children’s literature and educational writings for young readers.

Main Text

Any literary creation is deeply intertwined with the life of its creator. To understand a work of literature fully, it is essential to comprehend the life and intellectual orientation of its author, as the two remain mutually complementary. Therefore, before entering into a discussion of Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya’s literary contributions, it is necessary to present a brief overview of his personal life, professional career, and literary pursuits.

Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya was born on 1 February 1909 in the district of Faridpur, now in Bangladesh. His literary sensibility developed during childhood within a rich familial environment steeped in intellectual and literary engagement. His father, Bishweshwar Bhattacharya, and his elder brother Monoranjan Bhattacharya were respectively a Deputy Magistrate and a professor at Ripon College (now Surendranath College), where Monoranjan taught Economics and Political Science. Alongside their professional careers, both were accomplished writers. Bishweshwar Bhattacharya’s compilations Manikchander Gan and Gopichander Gan enriched the corpus of Bengali literature, particularly the domain of folk literature. Monoranjan Bhattacharya, in addition to writing several short stories, became renowned for creating the Japanese detective character “Hukakashi” in Bengal. Consequently, under their influence, Kshitindranarayan began his literary journey at a very early age.

Kshitindranarayan was the youngest among the five sons of Bishweshwar Bhattacharya. His eldest brother Hemendranarayan served as a Reader in Law at Banaras Hindu University. Due to his father’s transferable job, Kshitindranarayan studied in several schools before finally passing the Entrance Examination from South Suburban School in Kolkata. From his school days he began contributing writings to various prominent journals and magazines. In a letter addressed to Pritha Bal, daughter of Dhiren Bal, he wrote:

“Since my school days I had become somewhat known in the literary world... Initially I wrote only poetry, but later, on the advice of several senior writers and teachers, I began writing prose. When I studied science in college, I was inspired to write on popular science.”¹

Kshitindranarayan completed his B.Sc. and M.Sc. in Chemistry from Presidency College and the University of Calcutta respectively. In 1931 he secured first position in Applied Chemistry in the M.Sc. examination. Subsequently, he engaged in research in chemistry under the guidance of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray and Dr. Hemendrakumar. Although he later received opportunities to teach in several colleges, he declined them and instead entered the book trade. His family owned a publishing house named Kalitara Press, from which he published works by several writers.

From a memoir by Leela Majumdar we learn that her book *Badyinather Bori* was first published by Kshitindranarayan. Later, when it did not sell well, Dilip Gupta of Signet Press republished it under the title *Din-Dupure*, with a cover designed by Satyajit Ray.² Despite his lack of business experience, Kshitindranarayan proved to be a commendable publisher. Leela Majumdar remarked:

“Kshitīn produced a beautiful book—sturdy board cover, excellent binding, flawless printing. But the market is the market after all. Though competent, he was an inexperienced publisher; he could print books, but he could not sell them.”³

Eventually, facing financial losses, Kshitindranarayan closed his publishing business and sold the shop, after which he entered the teaching profession. He first taught Chemistry at Ashutosh College, then at Jogamaya Devi College, and finally at B.E.S. College. During this period, his literary career as a writer of science-based and science-fiction literature took a distinct and significant shape.

From that time onward he regularly contributed science fiction and other writings to various journals such as the family magazine *Ramdhanu*, as well as *Mukul*, *Shishusathi*, *Sandesh*, *Shuktara*, *Kishor Bharati*, *Kishor Gyan-Bigyan*, the annual publications of *Deb Sahitya Kutir*, *Betar Jagat*, *Jugantar*, and *Anandamela*. Though he generally wrote under his own name, he occasionally used the pseudonyms “Kautilya” and “Rasodar Sharma” while writing science fiction.⁴ The inspiration for his science-oriented literary writing came from figures such as Professor Charuchandra Bhattacharya, Kabishikhar Kalidas Ray, Kumudranjan Mallik, and Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.⁵

Below is a possible list of his published works—both original and edited—as well as his science-fiction stories, novels, translations, and essays published in various journals and anthologies. A preliminary version of this list had earlier been compiled by Ansar-ul-Haq.⁶

Published Books

1. *Galpa-Svalpa* (joint story collection with Monoranjan Bhattacharya), *Ramdhanu Karyalaya*, 1930.
2. *Bigyanburo*, *Ramdhanu Karyalaya*, 1932.
3. *Chhutih Galpa* (joint story collection with Monoranjan Bhattacharya), *Ramdhanu Karyalaya*, 1933.
4. *Bigyaner Joyjatra*, *Ramdhanu Karyalaya*, 1934.
5. *Akasher Galpa*, *Ramdhanu Karyalaya*, 1936.
6. *Dhumketu*, *Kalitara Press*, 1944.
7. *Rat Jokhon Satta*, *Deb Sahitya Kutir*, 1945.
8. *Oil Painting* (translated play), *Ramdhanu Karyalaya*, 1947.
9. *The Iliad* (translation), *Abhyuday Prakash Mandir*, 1953.
10. *The Odyssey* (translation), *Abhyuday Prakash Mandir*, 1954.
11. *The Black Tulip* (translation), *Abhyuday Prakash Mandir*, 1954.
12. *Mahabigyanī Newton* (biography), *Orient Book Co.*, 1958.
13. *Barodighir Raybari*, *Abhyuday Prakash Mandir*, 1959.
14. *Mahakasher Katha*, *Literacy Publication / West Bengal Literacy Eradication Society*.
15. *Luptadhan* (story collection), *Shaibya Prakashan*, 1981.
16. *Bigyan Aj-o Rannaghare*, *Bangiya Bigyan Parishad*, 1988.
17. *Tusharloker Rahasya*, *Shaibya Prakashan*.
18. *Meghnad*, *Shaibya Prakashan*.
19. *Janmadiner Upahar*, *Ramdhanu Karyalaya*.
20. *Chhotoder Bishwakosh* (*Children’s Encyclopedia*, 6 volumes; edited; illustrations by Purnachandra Chakrabarti).

Science-Fiction Stories, Novellas, and Essays Published in Periodicals

Kshitindranarayan’s first published science-fiction story was “*Kashmiri Rahasya*,” which appeared in the family magazine *Ramdhanu* in 1931 (Bengali year 1338). Subsequently he wrote numerous science-fiction narratives, including *Patagoniar Rahasya Manab*, *Chandashok*, *Amar Dweeper Kahini*, *Jahaj-Dubir Rahasya*, *Ghumanta Puri*, *Himghar*, *Krushniyam Natoboriyam*, *Mahakash Abhijan*, *Mangal-Grah-er Prani*, *Abhishapta Guha*, *Bamner Dweep*, *Danober Dweep*, *Miniluna*, *Professor X*, *Jibanta Fossil*, *Kongoboner Rahasya*, *Grhantare*, and many others (a detailed list includes approximately one hundred works).

These works appeared in various children’s magazines, annual issues, and anthologies, demonstrating the breadth and continuity of his engagement with science-oriented storytelling.

Editorial Work and the Magazine Ramdhanu

Kshitindranarayan's contribution to Bengali literature extended beyond authorship. His editorial role in the family magazine Ramdhanu was particularly significant. The magazine was founded by his father Bishweshwar Bhattacharya and first appeared in the Bengali month of Magh, 1334 (1927), as an illustrated monthly periodical for children and adolescents. Initially edited by Bishweshwar Bhattacharya for two years, the responsibility was later taken over by his second son Monoranjan Bhattacharya.

At that time Kshitindranarayan was still a college student, so he did not assume editorial responsibility; however, he served as the working manager of the magazine from its inception.⁷ From the beginning he contributed poems, essays, biographies, scientific articles, and travel writing.

When Monoranjan Bhattacharya died prematurely at the age of thirty-five in 1345 B.S., the editorial responsibility of Ramdhanu fell upon Kshitindranarayan. He continued to edit the magazine until his death, for nearly fifty years. Despite the profound grief caused by the death of his daughter and editorial collaborator Dr. Sucheta Mitra, he continued his editorial duties with dedication.

As an editor he was conscientious, impartial, and deeply committed to literary quality. At times he personally visited the homes of writers and artists to collect manuscripts or illustrations. His memoir *Chhotoder Bandhu Khagendranath* recounts an amusing anecdote about visiting the artist Phanibhushan Gupta to obtain illustrations for Ramdhanu, where he also met Khagendranath.⁸

In selecting contributions for publication, Kshitindranarayan prioritized literary merit above all else. Leela Majumdar observed:

"Writers are often somewhat intolerant—perhaps even slightly jealous—of other talented or famous writers. Kshitin was just the opposite. Being entirely indifferent to material gain, he never worried about such matters... Instead of filling his magazine with the works of already popular writers for profit, he introduced promising but unknown young writers to the reading public."⁹

During his editorial tenure, Ramdhanu featured works by notable authors such as Leela Majumdar, Premendra Mitra, Ashapura Devi, Shibram Chakraborty, Kumudranjan Mallik, Dhirendralal Dhar, Rabindranath Ray, Upendrachandra Mallik, Bande Ali Mia, and many others.

He also introduced a section titled "Panchmishali Bibhag," which emphasized scientific awareness among children. The magazine regularly included poetry, stories, novels, biographies, travel narratives, sports, history, geography, quizzes, and illustrated identification sections featuring famous personalities.

Contribution to the Institution of Children's Literature

Another significant contribution of Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya was the establishment of the Shishu Sahitya Parishad in 1351 B.S., with the aim of bringing together writers of children's literature. He served as its secretary for the first eight years before Khagendranath Mitra assumed the position. The office of the Parishad operated from his residence on Townsend Road in Kolkata.

According to Khagendranath Mitra, Kshitindranarayan personally bore a large portion of the institution's expenses without governmental assistance.¹¹ Leela Majumdar vividly described the literary gatherings at his house:

"In the drawing room of his house, almost every day throughout the year, a gathering of children's literature enthusiasts would take place. The cupboards were filled with children's books, the lights were paid for by him, and tea and refreshments were usually arranged at his expense."¹²

The Parishad played a vital role in nurturing new writers and organizing exhibitions of children's art. It also participated in the All-India Exhibition at Eden Gardens after India's independence. Occasionally theatrical performances were organized; on one occasion Rabindranath Tagore's play *Bisarjan* was staged with participation from prominent literary figures.¹³

The Parishad also published several journals, including *Shishu Bichitra* and *Ananda*. A compilation of rare writings titled *Aharani* was later published to preserve older texts.¹⁴

Literary Contribution and Recognition

Although Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya is primarily recognized as a writer of science-fiction stories, he contributed to many other genres of children’s literature. In magazines such as *Ramdhanu* and others, he wrote essays on science, travel narratives, biographies, and translations. Along with his brother Monoranjan Bhattacharya he co-authored several fairy-tale collections, including *Galpa-Svalpa* and *Chhutir Galpa*. His first illustrated collection of scientific essays was *Bigyan Buro*, followed by works such as *Bigyaner Joyjatra*, *Akash er Galpa*, *Abiskarer Galpa*, and *Mahakashar Katha*.

He also wrote a historical novel titled *Barodighir Raybari*, set during the transitional period marking the end of Muslim rule in India and the beginning of foreign colonial rule in Bengal. Among his translations, the Bengali versions of Homer’s epics *The Iliad* and *The Odyssey* are particularly notable. Another significant contribution was his editorial work on the six-volume *Children’s Encyclopedia*.

Kshitindranarayan presided over the Children’s Literature Section at the Krishnanagar and Jalpaiguri sessions of the Bangiya Sahitya Sammelan. He also served as the inaugurator of the Children’s Literature Section during the Golden Jubilee and the 53rd sessions of the All-India Bangiya Sahitya Sammelan, and he worked for many years as the President of the All-India Children’s Literature Conference and its West Bengal branch. Additionally, he served as Vice-President of the organization Science for Children.

For his outstanding contributions to children’s literature he received several awards: the Bhubaneswari Medal from the University of Calcutta in 1956, the Ranjit Memorial Award in 1378 B.S., the Fatik Memorial Award in 1982, and the Vidyasagar Award in 1987. He also received the Anandabichitra Medal and a Science Award from the Government of West Bengal.¹⁵

Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya passed away in Kolkata on 3 June 1990 at the age of eighty-one.

Conclusion

Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya’s contribution to Bengali literature extends far beyond the boundaries of individual authorship. As a writer, editor, and cultural organizer, he played a pivotal role in shaping the development of science-oriented children’s literature in Bengal. His writings successfully combined scientific knowledge with imaginative storytelling, thereby making complex scientific ideas accessible and engaging for young readers.

His editorial work in the magazine *Ramdhanu* created an important literary platform that nurtured several emerging writers and promoted diverse forms of children’s literature. Similarly, the establishment of the *Shishu Sahitya Parishad* reflects his commitment to institutionalizing children’s literary culture and encouraging collaborative literary activities.

Bhattacharya’s works demonstrate how literature can function as a medium for disseminating scientific awareness while simultaneously cultivating creativity and curiosity among readers. Within the broader context of Bengali literary history, his contributions occupy a distinctive place in the development of science fiction and popular science writing for children.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. A comparative study may be conducted between Kshitindranarayan Bhattacharya and other Bengali science-fiction writers such as Premendra Mitra and Adrish Bardhan.
2. Further research may examine the scientific ideas and technological imagination reflected in his science-fiction narratives.
3. The role of the magazine *Ramdhanu* in shaping twentieth-century Bengali children’s literary culture deserves a separate detailed study.
4. A thematic analysis of Bhattacharya’s works could explore how scientific curiosity, adventure, and ethical values are integrated in his narratives.
5. Digitization and archival research on his scattered writings in magazines could help recover many lesser-known works and provide a more comprehensive understanding of his literary legacy..

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